

All of the restorer lines of the hybrids to be produced are sown on the same day. Seedlings for each are transplanted 25-30 d after sowing within a 1-m² area, and spaced at 15 × 15 cm in alternate rows, leaving a 20-cm space all around the edge. The A lines of the hybrids to be produced are sown

2. Position of A (●) and R (x) lines in an isolated chamber.

on five or six different dates at a 6- to 7-d interval starting 2 wk before the seeding of the R lines. The aim is to achieve proper synchronization for the different A and R lines.

At the boot leaf stage of R lines, 2-m-high barriers are erected on three sides of the 1-m² plots, leaving a gap of 20 cm from the ground (Fig. 1). The open side is partially covered by the bamer from the adjacent plot. This space can be conveniently used for cultural operations, including supplementary pollination. Just before panicle emergence of the R lines, plants of the desired A line, which are at the same growth stage as the R lines, are moved and planted in the vacant alternate rows. To ensure higher outcrossing, supplementary

pollination using a stick should be carried out at anthesis 3-4 times/d for a week.

Within each 1-m² plot, there are 15 plants of the R line in 3 rows and 10 plants of the A line in 2 rows (Fig. 2). With a very conservative estimate of only 5 tillers/plant of the A line, 80 spikelets/panicle, and only a 40% outcrossing rate, about 1,600 seeds weighing 30-35 g can be easily obtained.

For conducting an OYT, 20-25 g of seed are more than adequate. The method proposed can be used to produce many hybrids for OYT. The advantages are

- comparatively pure seed of numerous F₁ hybrids can be produced in a limited area,
- the problem of obtaining proper synchronization of parental lines in hybrid seed production can be easily overcome, and
- F₁ seed for conducting OYT can be produced with the very limited quantity of R line seed available initially. ■

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Proline content in rice seedlings grown under saline conditions

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Severe salinity stress induces numerous metabolic irregularities in plants. Researchers have assumed that a large (up to 100 times the normal) accumulation of free-

proline is one of the most dramatic characteristics of the stress.

We surface-sterilized 20 seeds for each of four rice varieties: salt-tolerant Pokkali and IR42 and salt-sensitive MI 48 and Perla. After sterilization, these varieties were grown in plastic pots filled with gravel and Hoagland nutrient solution enriched with 0.7% NaCl solution. Other seeds were sown under the same conditions without salts. A pH value of 5.0 was maintained for both. Plants were placed in growth cham-

bers with 30/25 °C day/night temperature, 14 h of light, and 70% relative humidity. The experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications across three seasons. All measurements were taken 7 and 21 d after transplanting.

Plant material (0.5 g) was homogenized in 10 ml of 3% aqueous sulfosalicylic acid solution and filtered. Two ml of filtrate were reacted in 2 ml acid-ninhydrin and 2 ml of glacial acetic acid for 1 h at 100 °C. The reaction was terminated in an ice bath. To the reaction mixture, 4 ml of toluene were added and mixed vigorously with a test tube stirrer for 15-20 s. The chromophore containing toluene was aspirated from the aqueous phase, warmed to room temperature, and the absorbance read at 520 nm using toluene for a blank.

The proline concentration was determined from a standard curve and calculated on a fresh weight basis as

$$\text{mmol proline/g fresh weight material} = \frac{[(\text{mg proline/ml} \times \text{ml toluene}) / 115.5 \text{ mg/mmol}] / [\text{g sample} / 5]}{1}$$

The proline content for all varieties exposed to salt stress significantly increased (see table). The highest proline concentrations were observed in salt-sensitive varieties

Proline concentration in rice seedlings cultivated under normal and stress conditions.^a

Variety	Proline concentration (mg/g fresh matter)					
	7d			21 d		
	Control	Stress	% over control	Control	Stress	% over control
Pokkali	52.11 c	98.87 d	189	66.10 c	117.60 d	177
IR42	58.98 b	106.00 c	179	68.70 b	163.27 b	237
MI 48	45.03 d	156.68 a	347	59.46 d	180.11 a	302
Perla	68.19 a	153.28 b	224	71.10 a	194.44 c	273
SE	+0.92	+0.54		+0.42	+0.88	
CV(%)	2.84	0.72		1.45	0.93	

^a Values followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level according to DMRT.

Perla and MI 48 (between 224 and 347% more than the control at 7 d and 273 and 302% at 21 d). Pokkali and IR42 showed proline values of 179-189% more than the control at 7 d and 177-237% at 21 d.

The trials indicated that the salt-tolerant varieties do not necessarily accumulate large amounts of free-proline relative to salt-sensitive varieties. In general, free-proline content increased in salt-sensitive

varieties compared with that in salt-tolerant varieties and thus may not always be a suitable marker in examining salt resistance in rice. ■

Photosynthetic rate and respiration of some F₁ hybrid rices

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We studied the photosynthetic rate (Pn) and maintenance respiration (MR) of 11 hybrids developed from five cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines (IR64 A, PMS3 A, V20 A, Deepa A, and PMS 10 A) and their corresponding pollen parents under field conditions during the 1992 wet season.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Seedlings were transplanted at a spacing of 15 × 15 cm in 3-m² plots in the main field. Sixty kg N/ha were applied. We measured the Pn of the second

(n-1) leaf 35 d after planting (DAP) and that of the flag leaf (n leaf) at flowering with a LI-6000 photosynthesis system at near saturated light (1,000 μE/m² per s).

Maintenance respiration was measured directly from the CO₂ evolution rate using a differential respirometer (Gilson, USA). Leaves were excised in the evening and kept in the dark for 12 h. A weighed quantity without the midrib was cut into 1-2 mm pieces and suspended in 1.8 ml of 0.2 M phosphate buffer at pH 7.0 in a Warburg flask. Twenty percent KOH (0.2 ml) was poured into a center well and a filter paper strip was added to the alkali to increase the surface area for rapid CO₂ absorption. After greasing the upper rim, the flask was attached to the manometer, and the side arm of the flask was closed with a plug. The flask was then immersed in a water bath at a

constant 30 °C. The system was shaken to promote rapid gas exchange between the fluid and the gas phase.

The manometer fluid fell, indicating the rapid consumption of oxygen in the chamber by the tissue. The rate of respiration was calculated by subtracting the initial reading from the final reading. At each growth stage, four measurements for both Pn and MR were taken per sample for all three replications. The yield and biomass were assessed at harvest (see table).

Significant variations in Pn, MR, and Pn/MR among the hybrids and parents were observed at both 35 DAP and at flowering. However, the means of these three parameters were generally higher at flowering than at 35 DAP and in hybrids than in male parents at flowering stage. Hybrid IR64 A/Rasi showed high Pn at 35 DAP while IR64

Photosynthetic rate (Pn) and maintenance respiration (MR) in relation to yield and biomass production in rice hybrids. Cuttack, India. 1992 wet season.

Hybrid/restorer	35 DAP ^a			Flowering			TDM ^b (g/m ²)	Yield (g/m ²)
	Pn (μmol CO ₂ /m ²)	MR/s	Pn/MR	Pn (μmol CO ₂ /m ²)	MR/s	Pn/MR		
<i>Hybrids</i>								
IR64 A/Savitri	14.8	3.9	3.8	26.0	2.3	11.1	981	401
PMS3A/IR9828-91-2-3	16.2	2.4	6.7	20.2	2.0	10.3	798	396
PMS3A/Saruchina	21.0	2.0	10.6	28.9	2.4	12.1	1035	538
V20 A/IET11057	19.9	2.1	9.3	21.7	2.8	7.7	816	361
Deepa A/IET11057	22.5	2.8	8.1	21.1	2.6	8.1	916	312
V20 A/IET10463	15.3	2.1	7.5	17.2	2.5	6.9	676	263
PMS10A/ARC10339	16.0	2.3	7.0	27.6	3.7	7.4	865	463
IR64 A/Rasi	26.5	2.5	10.6	20.0	2.5	7.9	616	246
IR64 A/Miz. 51	16.7	1.8	9.2	29.7	3.2	9.2	1001	436
IR64 A/IR25560-109-3-1-3-2	16.2	2.3	7.2	17.0	2.3	7.5	694	212
IR64 A/IR1846-300-1	23.8	2.3	10.3	20.8	2.8	7.5	814	316
<i>Restorers</i>								
Savitri	22.7	2.3	9.7	29.0	3.3	8.8	1121	412
IR9828-91-2-3	18.9	2.4	7.8	31.6	2.3	13.7	863	346
Saruchina	14.1	4.5	3.2	18.6	2.0	9.4	912	402
IET11057	16.6	2.1	8.0	17.6	2.6	6.7	921	342
IET10463	21.0	2.7	7.7	12.8	1.6	7.7	729	240
ARC10339	8.1	2.0	4.1	9.5	1.8	5.2	961	424
Rasi	21.1	2.3	8.4	16.8	3.0	5.6	693	262
Miz. 51	17.1	2.0	9.1	19.8	2.7	7.4	942	421
IR25560-109-3-1-3-2	30.2	2.9	10.4	25.1	3.2	7.9	746	242
IR1846-300-1	18.1	1.9	9.5	20.1	2.7	7.6	964	341
Grand mean	18.9	2.5	8.0	21.5	2.7	8.4	860	359
Mean of hybrids	19.0	2.4	8.2	22.7	2.8	8.7	837	343
Mean of restorers	18.9	2.3	7.8	20.1	2.5	7.3	885	351
CD at 5%	3.6	0.8	1.5	1.5	0.3	0.8	29	14

^a DAP = days after planting. ^b TDM = total dry matter.